

Supplementary materials

Loanwords in basic vocabulary as an indicator of borrowing profiles

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Quality Clear Probable Possible

Figure S1. Counts (#) and proportions (%) of loanwords in UraLex for the six studied languages.

Language	UraLex (n)	UraLex borrowings (n)	Sw-207 (n)	Sw-207 borrowings (n)	Sw-100 (n)	Sw-100 borrowings (n)
Estonian	351	102	223	69	108	34
North Saami	378	127	247	82	110	30
Erzya	409	78	265	58	119	27
Komi-Zyrian	380	59	255	43	119	17
Meadow Mari	404	114	260	70	122	24
Hungarian	366	65	242	31	110	14

Table S1. Total numbers of words filling the UraLex meaning slots (313 meanings) and two of its sublists, the Swadesh-207 and the Swadesh-100 as well as total numbers of loanwords in the lists for the six studied languages. The varying total numbers reflect the synonymy attribute of the UraLex dataset.

Comparison tables of UraLex, dictionary data and general counts from literature

Estonian

EES loanwords	Notable semantic fields	EES	UraLex Clear	UraLex	Sw-207 Clear	Sw- 207	Sw-100 Clear	Sw-100
Indo-European		16–40 (0.3–0.8)	1 (0.3)	18 (5.2)	0	14 (6.2)	0	9 (8.3)
Indo-Iranian	Animal husbandry	20–33 (0.4–0.6)	2 (0.6)	7 (2.1)	1 (0.4)	4 (1.7)	0	2 (1.9)
Iranian		2–6 (0–0.1)	0	3 (0.9)	0	3 (1.3)	0	1 (0.9)
Baltic	Various, e.g. Agriculture, animal husbandry, body parts, kinship	162–235 (3.3–4.5)	12 (3.4)	21 (6.0)	9 (4)	16 (7.1)	7 (6)	8 (7.4)
Germanic	Various, e.g. agriculture, trade, seafaring, social organization	193–315 (3.9–6)	10 (2.8)	38 (10.8)	5 (2.8)	24 (10.8)	3 (3)	14 (13)
North Germanic		29–62 (0.6–1.2)	0	1 (0.3)	0	1 (0.4)	0	0
East Slavic and Old Russian loans	Agriculture, trade, religion	41–54 (0.8–1)	0	3 (0.9)	0	3 (1.3)	0	1 (0.9)
Old Swedish		14–33 (0.3–0.6)	0	0	0	0	0	0
Swedish	Handicrafts, military	61–140 (1.2–2.7)	1 (0.28)	1 (0.3)	1 (0.3)	1 (0.4)	0	0
Estonian and Finland Swedish		22–35 (0.4–0.7)	0	0	0	0	0	0

Low German	Professions, tools, societal order	476–659 (9.6–12.5)	3 (0.85)	4 (1.2)	2 (0.9)	2 (0.9)	1 (1)	1 (0.9)
German	Various, e.g. trade (similar to Low German influence)	356–506 (6.8–10.2)	1 (0.28)	1 (0.3)	0	0	0	0
Baltic German		43–56 (0.9–1.1)	0	0	0	0	0	0
Russian	Various, e.g. Religion, societal order, housekeeping	228–274 (4.6–5.2)	0	0	0	0	0	0
Latvian	Housekeeping, food	31–43 (0.6–0.8)	0	1 (0.3)	0	0	0	0
Finnish	Abstract literary expressions	197–212 (4–4)	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other		6–18 (0.1–0.3)	0	4 (1.2)	0	2 (0.8)	0	0
Not borrowed		2682–2926 (51.1–58.8)	0	249 (70.5)	0	149 (69.1)	0	70 (66.7)
Total		4823–5403 (100)	29 (8.26)	351 (100)	18 (7.9)	223 (100)	11 (10)	108 (100)

Table S2. Counts and proportions of borrowings in the Estonian etymological dictionary (= EES) surveyed by Soosaar 2013; 4823–5403 stems total, the Estonian full UraLex data (313 meanings, 351 words), the Swadesh 207 sublist (223 words) and the Swadesh 100 sublist (108 words). The *EES loanwords* column reflects the current understanding of loanword layers in Estonian. The *Notable semantic fields* are marked according to the information given in the front matter of the Estonian etymological dictionary. Empty cells mean that clear semantic fields could not be distinguished or the source literature does not provide the information. The range in the *EES* column shows the minimum and maximum values; the clear borrowings in a category and all proposed borrowings. The numbers in the *UraLex* and *Swadesh-207* columns include all borrowings (clear, probable and possible) grouped according to the categories used in *EES*. The *Clear* columns indicate how many of the borrowings have clear status, which corresponds to the minimum value of the EES range. The values in brackets are percentages.

References for Table S2

EES = Metsämägi, Iiris, Meeli Sedrik, and Sven-Erik Soosaar. 2012. *Eesti Etümolooiasõnaraamat*. Tallinn: Eesti Keele Sihtasutus.

Soosaar, Sven-Erik. 2013. The Origins of Stems of Standard Estonian - a Statistical Overview. *Trames: A Journal of the Humanities and Social Sciences*; Tallinn 17 (3): 273–300.

Category	Average in EES	Average in UraLex	EES %	UraLex %
Germanic	254	24	4.70	6.84
Baltic	199	17	3.68	4.84
Indo-European	28	10	0.52	2.85
Indo-Iranian	27	5	0.50	1.42
Low German	568	4	10.51	1.14
Iranian	4	2	0.07	0.57
Other	12	2	0.22	0.57
North Germanic	46	1	0.85	0.28
Slavic & Old Russian	48	2	0.89	0.57
Swedish	153	1	2.83	0.28
German	481	1	8.90	0.28
Latvian	37	1	0.68	0.28
Russian	299	0	5.53	0.00
Finnish	205	0	3.79	0.00

Table S3. Average numbers of loanwords in a loanword category in the Estonian etymological dictionary (= EES) and the Estonian UraLex taken from the range in the EES column and UraLex and UraLex Clear columns in Table S2. The columns marked with % indicate the percentage that the average represents out of the maximum total number of words in EES and UraLex respectively. The percentages are plotted for visual comparison in Fig. 5.

North Saami

Borrowing source	Estimate in literature	Notable semantic fields	UraLex Clear	UraLex	Sw-207 Clear	Sw-207	Sw-100 Clear	Sw-100
Baltic	32-40		2	3	1	2	1	1
Balto-Slavic	5		0	1	0	1	0	0
Proto-Finnic and Finnish	Thousands	All	41	48	25	29	4	6
Germanic	28-63		3	9	1	6	1	3
Indo-European	61		0	20	0	15	0	6
Indo-Iranian and Iranian	Ca. 20		1	5	1	3	1	3
Proto-North Germanic and modern Scandinavian languages	Thousands	All, (notable fields in the older layers: animal husbandry, kinship, iron processing, seafaring)	36	37	22	22	8	8
Unknown language	Potentially hundreds	E.g. bird names, topography	0	1	0	0	0	0

Donor language family unclear	0	4	0	4	3	0
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Table S4. Counts of borrowings given in the literature, the North Saami UraLex data (313 meanings, 378 words), the Swadesh-207 sublist (247 words) and the Swadesh-100 sublist (110 words). *The Borrowing source* column represents the current understanding of the loanword layers in Saami. The *Estimate in literature* column indicates the numbers of borrowings in North Saami according to literature. The ranges for Baltic and Germanic borrowings represent clear borrowings and all proposed borrowings together in the reference literature. The *Notable semantic fields* are marked according to the literature in the *Source* column. Empty cells mean that clear semantic fields could not be distinguished or the source literature does not provide the information. The numbers in the *UraLex* and *Swadesh-207* columns include all borrowings (clear, probable and possible). The *Clear* columns indicate how many of the borrowings have clear status.

References for Table S4

- Aikio, Ante. 2012. An Essay on Saami Ethnolinguistic Prehistory. In Riho Grünthal and Petri Kallio (eds.), *A Linguistic Map of Prehistoric Northern Europe*. Suomalais-ugrilaisen seuran toimituksia 266: 63–117. Helsinki: Suomalais-Ugrilainen Seura.
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- Sammallahti, Pekka. 1998. *The Saami Languages: An Introduction*. Karasjok: Davvi girji cop.

Erzya

Borrowing source	Estimate in literature	Notable semantic fields	UraLex Clear	UraLex	Sw-207 Clear	Sw-207	Sw-100 Clear	Sw-100
Archaic Indo-European			0	15	0	10	0	4
Baltic	36		1	10	0	7	0	2
Finnic			0	1	0	1	0	1
Germanic	Single items, mediated through other Finnic languages	0	3	0	2	0	1	
Indo-Iranian and Iranian	Dozens distributed across Western Uralic, 7 confined to Mordvinic	Animal husbandry, kinship	4	13, one Indo-Iranian & Iranian confined only to Mordvinic	4	9	3	7
Russian	Thousands	All	22	25	15	19	5	7
Volga Bulgar	Only a few		2	4	2	2	1	1

Tatar	Ca. 300	Various e.g. housekeeping, religion, kinship	1	4	1	3	1	2
Other Turkic			2	4	2	4	0	1

Table S5. Counts of borrowings given in the literature, the Erzya Mordvin UraLex data (313 meanings, 378 words), the Swadesh-207 sublist (265 words) and the Swadesh-100 sublist (110 words). *The Borrowing source* column represents the current understanding of the loanword layers in Mordvinic with a focus on Erzya. The *Estimate in literature* column indicates the numbers of borrowings in Mordvinic according to the literature. The literature provides limited information on absolute numbers and therefore some entries are left empty. The *Notable semantic fields* are marked according to the literature in the *Source* column. Empty cells mean that clear semantic fields could not be distinguished or the source literature does not provide the information. The numbers in the *UraLex* and *Swadesh-207* columns include all borrowings (*clear, probable and possible*). The *Clear* columns indicate how many of the borrowings have clear status.

References for Table S5

- Décsy, Gyula. 1988. Slawischer Einfluss Auf Die Uralischen Sprachen. In Denis Sinor (ed.), *The Uralic Languages: Description, History, and Foreign Influences*. Handbuch Der Orientalistik 8: 616–635. Leiden: Brill.
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Komi

KESK category	Clear	All
Baltic-Finnic	57	86
Chuvash	30	50
Chuvash or Udmurt		1
Finnic or Karelian		1
Finnic or Russian		2
Germanic		2
Indo-European	6	34
Indo-Iranian	15	34
Iranian	38	42
Karelian	1	2
Karelo-Veps	3	6
Khanty	3	9
Mansi	9	11
Mansi or Khanty		1
Nenets	57	63
Nenets or Mansi		2
Ob-Ugric		4
Old Russian	10	14
Russian	165	194

Russian or Chuvash		3
Samoyedic	1	2
Veps	3	
Other		35
Altaic		2
Altaic or Yukaghir		1
Altaic or Yukag or Indo-European		2
Caucasian		1
Indo-European or Tungusic or Yukaghir		2
Indo-European or Turkic or Yukaghir		1
Mongolian		1
Tungusic		1
Turkic	1	15
Turkic or Mongolian		1
Yukaghir		9
Total borrowings	399	634

Total
of all
words
4038

Table S6. Counts of borrowings extracted from the Komi etymological dictionary (= KESK) and the source-language categories expressed in the dictionary grouped into the KESK category column. The *Clear* column gathers the loanwords for which the certainty or origin is not contested in the dictionary. The *All* column contains all loanwords in a category regardless of certainty as well as borrowings with unclear source languages.

Borrowing source	Estimate in literature	Notable semantic fields	KESK	UraLex Clear	UraLex	Sw-207 Clear	Sw-207	Sw-100 Clear	Sw-100
Archaic Indo-European			6–34 (0.1–0.8)	1 (0.3)	13 (3.6)	0	11 (4.4)	0	4 (4)
Germanic	Single items, mediated through other Finnic languages		0–2 (0–0.05)	0	1 (0.3)	0	1 (0.4)	0	0
Indo-Iranian and Iranian	Dozens distributed across Western Uralic. Under 50 confined to Permic acquired from chronologically different layers and Iranian varieties	Animal husbandry, kinship	53–76 (1.3–1.9)	8 (2.1)	18 (4.8)	5 (2)	11 (4.4)	0	7 (7)
Ob-Ugric (Khanty and Mansi)	Ca. 45	Reindeer herding, tundra lifestyle	16–25 (0.4–0.6)	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nenets and unclear Samoyedic	Ca. 85, of which 12 distributed widely across Komi dialects	Reindeer herding, tundra lifestyle	58–65 (1.4–1.6)	0	0	0	0	0	0
Russian	Thousands	All	165–194	17 (4.5)	19 (5.1)	12 (4.7)	14 (5.5)	3 (3)	4 (4)

		(4.1– 4.8)						
Old Russian		10–14 (0.2– 0.3)	0	0	0	0	0	0
Volga Bulgar	Ca. 20	30–50 (0.7– 1.2)	2 (0.5)	3 (0.8)	1 (0.8)	3 (1.2)	1 (1)	1 (1)
Western Uralic and Finnic	< 80 in Permic	64–98 (1.6– 2.4)	0	4 (1.1)	0	3 (1.2)	0	1 (1)
Other		1–44 (0–1.1)	0	1 (0.3)	0	0	0	0
Not borrowed		3635– 3436 (90– 85.1)		356– 318 (93.9– 83.7)		230– 210 (92.– 82.4)		115– 98 (96.6– 82.4)
Total		4038 (100)		380 (100)		255 (100)		119 (100)

Table S7. Counts (and proportions) of borrowings given in the literature, the Komi etymological dictionary (= KESK) the Komi Zyrian UraLex data (313 meanings, 380 words), the Swadesh-207 sublist (255 words) and the Swadesh-100 sublist (119 words). The *Borrowing source* column represents the current understanding of the loanword layers in Komi. The *Estimate in literature* column indicates the numbers of borrowings in Komi according to literature. The literature provides limited information on absolute numbers and therefore some entries are left empty. The *Notable semantic fields* are marked according to literature. Empty cells mean that clear semantic fields could not be distinguished or the source literature does not provide the information. The information in the *KESK* column is composed using the information from Table S6 and fitted according to the *Borrowing source* column. The Archaic Indo-European category in the *Borrowing source* column combines all items considered Proto-Indo-European or archaic Indo-European, because these categories are not distinguished in KESK. The *Western Uralic and Finnic* category contains KESK items labeled as Proto-Finnic, Veps, Karelian or unclear Finnic strata. The *Other* category contains dubious items regarding which the relationship is highly uncertain or rejected in current research. The range in the *KESK* column shows the minimum and maximum values; the clear borrowings in a category and all proposed borrowings. The numbers in the *UraLex* and *Swadesh-207* columns include all borrowings (clear, probable and possible). The *Clear* labels

indicate how many of the borrowings have clear status, which corresponds to the minimum value of the KESK range. The values in brackets are percentages.

References for Table S7

- Bartens, Raija. 2000. *Permiläisten kielten rakenne ja kehitys*. Suomalais-ugrilaisen seuran toimituksia 238. Helsinki: Suomalais-Ugrilainen Seura.
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- KESK = Lytkin, Vasilij. and F.S. Guljaev. 1970. *Kratkii etimologičeskii slovar komi jazyka*. Institut jazykoznanija An SSSR: Komi ficial. Moskva: Nauka.
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Category	Average in KESK	Average in Komi UraLex	KESK %	Komi UraLex %
Russian	180	18	4.46	4.74
Indo-Iranian & Iranian	65	13	1.61	3.42
Indo-European	20	6	0.50	1.58
Volga Bulgarian	40	3	0.99	0.79
Finnic & Western Uralic	81	2	2.01	0.53
Germanic	1	1	0.02	0.26
Other	23	1	0.57	0.26
Khanty & Mansi	21	0	0.52	0.00
Nenets & Samoyedic	62	0	1.54	0.00
Old Russian	12	0	0.30	0.00

Table S8. Average numbers of loanwords in a loanword category in the Komi etymological dictionary (= KESK) and the Komi UraLex taken from the range in the KESK column and UraLex and UraLex Clear columns in Table S7. The columns marked with % indicate the percentage that the average represents out of the maximum total number of words in KESK and UraLex respectively. The percentages are plotted for visual comparison in Fig. 5B.

References for Table S8

- KESK = Lytkin, Vasilij. and F.S. Guljaev. 1970. *Kratkii etimologičeskii slovar komi jazyka*. Institut jazykoznanija An SSSR: Komi ficial. Moskva: Nauka.
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Meadow Mari

Borrowing source	Estimate in literature	Notable semantic fields	Max in TschWB	TschWB Categories	TschWB counts and %	UraLex Clear	UraLex	Sw-207 Clear	Sw-207	Sw-100 Clear	Sw-100
Volga Bulgar and Chuvash	Ca. 500	Various, e.g. housekeeping, agriculture, human relations		Chuvash	488 (10.4)	39 (9.7)	49 (12.1)	25 (9.6)	32 (12.3)	11 (9)	14 (11)
Tatar	200-2100 depending on dialect	Various e.g. agriculture, housekeeping, transport, trade, human relations		Tatar	735 (15.7)	24 (5.9)	26 (6.3)	13 (5)	14 (5.4)	1 (1)	1 (1)
Russian	Over 1600	Practically all domains		Russian	975 (20.8)	6 (1.5)	7 (1.7)	0	1 (0.4)	0	0
Other				Other	141 (3.3)	2 (0.5)	5 (1.1)	1 (0.4)	3 (1.2)	1 (1)	1 (1)
Archaic Indo-European			21 (0.45)			1 (0.2)	12 (2.8)	0	9 (3.6)	0	3 (3)

Indo-Iranian and Iranian	Dozens distributed across Western Uralic, under 10 confined to Mari, some shared between Mari, Komi and Udmurt probably due areal contacts	Animal husbandry, kinship	33 (0.71)	4 (1)	14 (3.1), 3 Indo-Iranian items confined to Mari	3 (1.2)	8 (3.1)	2 (2)	4 (4)
Permic	44 from Permic and 30 from Udmurt proposed		9–10 (0.21)	0	1(0.3)	0	1 (0.4)		
		Not borrowed	2326 (49.8)		290 (72,7)		190 (73.6)		75 (61.5)
		Total count	4666		404		260		122

Table S9. Counts (and proportions) of borrowings given in the literature, the Mari dictionary (= TschWB) surveyed by Saarinen (2010), the Meadow Mari UraLex data (313 meanings, 404 words), the Swadesh-207 sublist (260 words) and Swadesh-100 sublist (122 words). The *Borrowing source* column represents the current understanding of the loanword layers in Mari. The *Estimate in literature* column indicates the numbers of borrowings in Mari according to literature. The literature provides limited information on absolute numbers and therefore some entries are left empty. The *Notable semantic fields* are marked according to the literature in the *Source* column. Empty cells mean that clear semantic fields could not be distinguished or the source literature does not provide the information. The *Max in TschWB* column contains information on loanwords suggested in other literature that are present in TschWB. The category marked as *Other* in TschWB contains all items of archaic Indo-European, Iranian and other Indo-European languages (e.g. Baltic) origin as well as items without a clear stratification. The *Other* category of UraLex includes the single Baltic and Germanic items likely mediated from other languages and other Turkic loanwords. The numbers in the *UraLex* and *Swadesh-207* columns include all borrowings (clear, probable and

possible) grouped according to the categories used in EES. The *Clear* columns indicate how many of the borrowings have clear status, which corresponds to the minimum value of the EES range. The values in brackets are percentages.

References for Table S9

- Bereczki, Gábor. 1992. *Grundzüge Der Tscheremissischen Sprachgeschichte: 2. Studia Uralo-Altaica 34*. Szeged: University of Szeged, Department of Altaic Studies and Department of Finno-Ugrian Philology.
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Hungarian

Borrowing source	Estimation in literature	Notable semantic fields	EWUng	UraLex Clear	UraLex	Sw-207 Clear	Sw-207	Sw-100 Clear	Sw-100
Archaic Indo-European			24 (labeled Iranian)	0	10 (2.7)	0	5 (2.1)	0	2 (2)
Indo-Iranian and Iranian	Ca. 40 from chronologically different layers, ca. 4 early loans confined to Hungarian	Animal husbandry, horse, kinship	(0.24%)	1 (0.3)	11 (3), Ca. 5 Iranian possibly confined to Hungarian	0	6 (2.4)	0	4 (4)
Slavic	Ca. 2000	Various fields, e.g., agriculture, Christianity, housing, societal order	900 (9.11)	8 (22)	8 (2.2)	3 (1.2)	3 (1.2)	1 (1)	1 (1)
Volga Bulgarian	Over 20	Body parts	386 (labeled Turkic)	1 (0.3)	2 (0.6)	0	1 (0.4)	0	0
West Old Turkic	Ca. 500	Various fields, e.g. agriculture, religion	(3.91%)	11 (3)	29 (7.9)	6 (2.5)	14 (5.9)	4 (4)	6 (6)

Cumanian, Pecheneg, Ottoman and other Turkic	Under 30	Clothing, food	1 (0.3)	4 (1.2)	0	2 (0.8)	0	1 (1)
German	500–600 until the 19th century	Various fields, e.g. military, court, art	1404 (14.22)	0	0	0	0	0
Latin	Ca. 200 in everyday use	Christianity, education	1076 (10.89)	0	0	0	0	0
Romani	Ca. 300	Various slang words	24 (0.24)	0	0	0	0	0
Romance languages		Food	327 (3.31)	0	0	0	0	0
Other			1115 (11.29)	0	1	0	0	0
Not borrowed			4619 (46.79)		301 (82.2)		211 (87.2)	96 (87.3)

Table S10. Counts (and proportions) of borrowings given in the literature, the Hungarian etymological dictionary (= EWUng); 9876 entries in total surveyed by Keresztes (1998), the Hungarian UraLex data (313 meanings, 336 words), the Swadesh-207 sublist (242 words) and the Swadesh-100 sublist (110 words). The *Borrowing source* column represents the current understanding of the loanword layers in Hungarian. The *Estimate in literature* column indicates the numbers of borrowings in Hungarian according to literature. The literature provides limited information on absolute numbers and therefore some entries are left empty. The *Notable semantic fields* are marked according to the literature. Empty cells mean that clear semantic fields could not be distinguished or the source literature does not provide the information. The EWUng column represents the categorization given in Keresztes (1998) and groups older Indo-European borrowings into one category and all Turkic categories into another. The *Other* category contains loanwords from source languages with a minor impact on the Hungarian vocabulary, e.g. so-called international words. The numbers in the UraLex and Swadesh-207 columns include all borrowings (clear, probable and possible) grouped according to the categories used in EES. The *Clear* columns indicate how many of the

borrowings have clear status, which corresponds to the minimum value of the EES range. The values in brackets are percentages.

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Figure S2. The percentages of borrowed and non-borrowed items in the six studied languages. The black dark-gray and medium-gray bars represent the borrowed proportion in the full UraLex lists, the Swadesh-207 and the Swadesh-100 sublists, respectively. The proportion of items with no evidence of borrowing is marked in light gray for both lists.

Source	Est	EstSW207	EstSW100	Komi	KomSW207	KomSW100
Indo-European	[Solid black]					
Indo-Iranian	[Solid grey]			[Diagonal lines]		
Iranian	[Solid grey]			[Diagonal lines]		
Indo-European & Indo-Iranian & Iranian	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Indo-Iranian & Iranian	[Diagonal lines]			[Solid black]		
Germanic	[Solid black]			[Solid grey]		
Low German	[Grid pattern]			[Diagonal lines]		
North Germanic	[Solid grey]			[Diagonal lines]		
German	[Grid pattern]			[Diagonal lines]		
Swedish	[Grid pattern]			[Diagonal lines]		
Slavic	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Slavic & Old Russian	[Solid grey]			[Diagonal lines]		
Old Russian	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Russian	[Diagonal lines]			[Solid grey]		
Balto-Slavic	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Baltic	[Solid black]			[Diagonal lines]		
Latvian	[Solid grey]			[Diagonal lines]		
Latin	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Romance	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Romani	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Turkic	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Volga Bulgar	[Diagonal lines]			[Solid grey]		
Chuvash & Volga Bulgar	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Tatar	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Unknown language	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
"International" words	[White]			[White]		
Finnic & Western Uralic	[Diagonal lines]			[Grid pattern]		
Finnic & Finnish	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Finnish	[White]			[Diagonal lines]		
Permic	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Khanty & Mansi	[Diagonal lines]			[White]		
Nenets & Samoyedic	[Diagonal lines]			[White]		

Source	Nsaami	SaamSW 207	SaamSW100	Erzya	ErzSW207	ErzSW100
Indo-European	[Solid black fill]					
Indo-Iranian	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Iranian	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Indo-European & Indo-Iranian & Iranian	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Indo-Iranian & Iranian	[Solid black fill]					
Germanic	[Grid pattern]			[Grid pattern]		
Low German	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
North Germanic	[Solid black fill]		[Grey fill]	[Diagonal lines]		
German	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Swedish	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Slavic	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Slavic & Old Russian	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Old Russian	[Diagonal lines]			[Grey fill]		
Russian	[Diagonal lines]			[Grey fill]		
Balto-Slavic	[Grid pattern]		[White fill]	[Diagonal lines]		
Baltic	[Grid pattern]			[Solid black fill]		[Grid pattern]
Latvian	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Latin	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Romance	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Romani	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Turkic	[Diagonal lines]			[Grid pattern]		
Volga Bulgar	[Diagonal lines]			[Solid black fill]		[Grid pattern]
Chuvash & Volga Bulgar	[Diagonal lines]			[Grid pattern]		
Tatar	[Diagonal lines]			[Grid pattern]		
Unknown language	[Grid pattern]		[White fill]	[Diagonal lines]		
"International" words	[White fill]			[White fill]		
Finnic & Western Uralic	[Diagonal lines]			[Grid pattern]		
Finnic & Finnish	[Grey fill]		[Solid black fill]	[Diagonal lines]		
Finnish	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Permic	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Khanty & Mansi	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		
Nenets & Samoyedic	[Diagonal lines]			[Diagonal lines]		

Source	Mari	MarSW207	MarSW100	Hun	HunSW207	HunSW100
Indo-European						
Indo-Iranian						
Iranian						
Indo-European & Indo-Iranian & Iranian						
Indo-Iranian & Iranian						
Germanic						
Low German						
North Germanic						
German						
Swedish						
Slavic						
Slavic & Old Russian						
Old Russian						
Russian						
Balto-Slavic						
Baltic						
Latvian						
Latin						
Romance						
Romani						
Turkic						
Volga Bulgar						
Chuvash & Volga Bulgar						
Tatar						
Unknown language						
"International" words						
Finnic & Western Uralic						
Finnic & Finnish						
Finnish						
Permic						
Khanty & Mansi						
Nenets & Samoyedic						

Figure S3. Summary of congruent, overrepresented, underrepresented and missing loanword layers in UraLex, Swadesh-207 and Swadesh-100 lists in comparison to large dictionary data for Estonian, North Saami, Meadow Mari, Komi-Zyrian and Hungarian. For North Saami and Erzya the representation of the loanword layers is roughly approximated qualitatively against general estimates given in literature. The categories indicated in the *Source* column follow the categories used in the quantitative comparisons in Section 3.5 and supplemented with the categories established for North Saami and Erzya in Tables S4 and S5. The source categories are grouped roughly according to the donor-language families and their subgroups. The heterogeneous Other category is omitted from this summary. Dark-gray cells indicate congruence of the loanword layers in UraLex and comparison data. Black denotes

overrepresentation, raster underrepresentation and white denotes missing categories. The cells with diagonal lines strike out irrelevant category names for the particular comparison.

Figure S4A. Comparison of prominent loanword categories in etymological dictionaries (y-axes) and the Swadesh-207 basic vocabulary lists (x-axes) for Estonian and Komi. The scale on the y-axes stands for the percentage that the average number of loanwords in a category represents for the respective Estonian and Komi dictionaries. The scale on the x-axes represents the percentages of average numbers for the Estonian and Komi Swadesh-207.

Figure S4B. Comparison of prominent loanword categories in (etymological) dictionaries (y-axes) and the Swadesh-207 basic vocabulary lists (x-axes) for Mari and Hungarian. The scale on the y-axis stands for the total number of loanwords in a category in the respective Mari and Hungarian dictionaries. The scale on the x-axis represents the total numbers of loanwords in the Mari and Hungarian Swadesh-207 data.

Figure S5A. Comparison of prominent loanword categories in etymological dictionaries (y-axes) and the Swadesh-100 basic vocabulary lists (x-axes) for Estonian and Komi. The scale on the y-axes stands for the percentage that the average number of loanwords in a category represents for the respective Estonian and Komi dictionaries. The scale on the x-axes represents the percentages of average numbers for the Estonian and Komi Swadesh-100.

Figure S5B. Comparison of prominent loanword categories in (etymological) dictionaries (y-axes) and the Swadesh-100 basic vocabulary lists (x-axes) for Mari and Hungarian. The scale on the y-axes stands for the total number of loanwords in a category in the respective Mari and Hungarian dictionaries. The scale on the x-axes represents the total numbers of loanwords in the Mari and Hungarian Swadesh-100 data.

Section S1. The borrowing profile mediated by the Swadesh-100 lists

The UraLex 2.0 dataset covers three popular basic vocabulary lists: Swadesh-100, Swadesh-207 and Leipzig-Jakarta as well as an expansion with the WOLD401-500 meanings. The Swadesh-100 is a well-established list and has stricter conditions which meanings are considered basic.

UraLex 2.0 allows synonymy in the meaning slots which is reflected by the borrowing percentages in the Swadesh-100 lists: The percentages in the Swadesh-100 list are similar to the borrowing percentages in the full UraLex 2.0 lists. For Estonian and Erzya, the Swadesh-100 has slightly more borrowings than the full list: 31.5 % vs. 29.5 % for Estonian and 22.7 % vs. 19.1 % for Erzya (Fig. S2). For North Saami, Komi, Mari and Hungarian, the Swadesh-100 has less borrowing than the full list. Despite the similar general borrowing percentages (24 % on average in the complete UraLex 2.0 lists vs 22 % in the Swadesh-100 lists), the representation of the loanwords layers reveals both similarities with and differences from the full lists. The borrowing profile in the Hungarian Swadesh-100 list appears as most similar to the profile captured by the complete list. However, this is likely caused by the lack detail in the large vocabulary stock we compare UraLex 2.0 with and the lower success of detecting the borrowing profile for Hungarian in general (see main text Discussion).

According to our quantitative comparison between the Swadesh-100 list and the large vocabulary stocks (presented in Figs. S5A1-2 and S5B1-2), the loanword layers with relatively small numbers on loanwords overall are congruent in size just as in the full list: Indo-Iranian and Iranian layers in Estonian, Volga Bulgar in Komi and Permian in Mari. There are two instances where the largest categories in a language overall also are congruent between the large word stock and Swadesh-100: Volga Bulgar & Chuvash for Mari and Russian in Erzya. We infer the latter two on the basis of qualitative comparison (Fig. S3B).

The majority of the same layers underrepresented in the complete UraLex 2.0 are so in Swadesh-100 as well (Fig S3). These are the layers of Low German and Swedish in Estonian, Finnic & Western Uralic in Komi, Tatar in Mari and Slavic in Hungarian according to the quantitative comparisons. In our qualitative comparisons, these layers are Germanic and Baltic in North Saami and the Germanic, Turkic, Tatar, Finnic & Western Uralic layers for Erzya. In one case, a layer is accurately shown as congruent in the full list but underrepresented in Swadesh-100: Russian in Komi (still the largest layer overall). In Erzya, the Baltic and Volga Bulgar layers are underrepresented in Swadesh-100 while overrepresented in the full list.

The loanword layers already missing from the complete lists are naturally also missing from the Swadesh-100 lists. Further, many smaller layers underrepresented in the complete lists are completely missing from Swadesh-100. The Estonian Swadesh-100 list has three more layers missing when compared to the full list (North Germanic, German, Slavic & Old Russian and Latvian). Komi is additionally missing the uncertain Germanic influence, Mari is missing Russian and the North Saami Swadesh-100 does not have the minor Balto-Slavic layer or influence from the Unknown non-Uralic, non Indo-European language.

The quantitative comparison shows that in the Swadesh-100 the Indo-European, Germanic and Baltic layers are overrepresented in Estonian. In Komi, Mari and Hungarian the categories involving Indo-European and Indo-Iranian and Iranian are also strongly overrepresented. These layers are overrepresented for North Saami and Erzya as well according to our qualitative comparison. Other overrepresented layers are the large combined category of Turkic influence in Hungarian. The Finnic & Finnish layer is the largest layer in the North Saami Swadesh-100 list and it can be interpreted as overrepresented. The full North Saami list represents the size of this layer accurately. However, both borrowing sources have a vast impact on North Saami.

In summary, the most influential contacts are reflected by the borrowing profiles in the Swadesh-100 lists similarly to the full UraLex 2.0 lists, which is to be expected. These loanword layers with large numbers of loanwords tend to be either congruent in size between Swadesh-100 and the large vocabulary stocks (North Germanic in North Saami, Russian in Erzya, Chuvash & Volga Bulgar in Mari) or overrepresented (e.g. Germanic and Baltic in Estonian, Finnic & Finnish in North Saami the Turkic category in Hungarian). The oldest loanword layers appear highly overrepresented perhaps at the expense of other influential contacts (e.g. the large Russian layer is underrepresented in Komi) whereas those layers already underrepresented in the complete UraLex 2.0 lists also are underrepresented or missing from the Swadesh-100 lists.

Aims and analyses	Labels	Data points	Results and figures
Detailed overview of the loanword layers present in UraLex	Higher resolution, language-specific labels	Presence/absence of loanword layer in UraLex; n of loanwords in UraLex; presence of clear-status loanwords in a category in UraLex	3.2–3.4, Fig. S1
Evaluating the macro-borrowing profile of UraLex	Broad, subgroup-level labels	Percentage of loanwords in a category in UraLex, presence of loanwords in UraLex on the level of donor-language subgroup	3.2–3.4, Fig. 4.
Qualitative comparison between North Saami, Erzya and estimations on sizes of loanword layers in literature	Higher resolution, language-specific labels	Total n of loanwords in a loanword category in UraLex and literature	3.2–3.4, Tables S4, S5

Quantitative comparison between Estonian, Komi Zyrian loanword layers in UraLex and dictionary surveys	Labels in EES based on the survey by Soosaar (2013). Adapted labels for the Komi dictionary data (KESK) and UraLex	Percentages using the average from the range between total n of loanwords and clear status loanwords in a category in UraLex and dictionary surveys	3.5, Fig. 4A, Tables S2, S3, S7
Quantitative comparison between Meadow Mari, Hungarian loanword layers in UraLex and dictionary surveys	Labels provided in the surveys and adapted labels for UraLex	Total n of loanwords in a loanword categories provided in surveys	3.5, Fig. 4B, Tables S9, S8, S10

Table S11. Summary analyses and information types needed to study the borrowing profiles of the focal languages. The first two rows of the column “Aims and analyses” focuses on determining which loanword layers are present in UraLex in general in comparison to the whole language and the latter two on analyzing their sizes and representation. The macro-borrowing profile refers to detection of donor language influence on a rougher subgroup-level. “Labels” specify the names of the loanword layers required in different analyses and presentations. “Data points” summarizes the information type taken from UraLex. “Results and figures” refers to the location of information in the main text and the Supplement.

A sample of other languages in UraLex and their loanword strata

Source	Courland Livonian	Skolt Saami	Udmurt	Vakh-Vasyugan Khanty	Tundra Nenets
Baltic	19 (8)	4 (3)	?	-	-
Balto-Slavic	?	1	?	?	?
Estonian	3	-	-	-	-
Finnic	?	45 (39)	1	-	-
Germanic	30 (9)	5 (3)	?	-	-
Germanic or Baltic	1	?	?	-	-
Germanic or Finnic	?	1	?	-	-
Germanic or Scandinavian	2	1	-	-	-
Indo-European	7 (1)	3	2	2	1

Indo-Iranian	7 (2)	3 (2)	11 (8)	1	1
Indo-Iranian or Indo-European	1	3	2	?	?
Indo-Iranian or Iranian	1	1	2	?	?
Iranian	?	?	8 (2)	5 (1)	?
Komi	-	-	-	6 (6)	?
Latvian	16 (16)	-	-	-	-
Low German or Lithuanian	1	-	-	-	-
North-West-Indo-European	3	6	2	-	-
Permic	-	-	-	1	?
Pre-Tocharian	-	-	-	-	1
Proto-Indo-European	10	5	4	3	2
Russian	?	10 (9)	6 (6)	?	?
North Germanic	?	19 (18)	-	-	-
Slavic	1	?	?	?	?
Tatar	-	-	12 (11)	1 (1)	-
Tungusic	-	-	-	4	?
Turkic	-	-	?	?	1 (1)
Unknown language		1			
Volga Bulgar	-	-	6 (4)	?	?
Western Uralic	-	?	2	-	-

Table S12. Counts of loanwords in a five-language sample in UraLex with less literature available and not selected as study languages. The numbers in brackets indicate the counts of clear items. Bashkir and Mari borrowings are not present in the data for Udmurt. Also disputed Yeniseian borrowings and possible Volga Bulgar Turkic loans are missing from Khanty. - means that no loanwords from a particular source are expected to be found. ? indicates that a layer is missing from the data but there is some possibility of borrowing. For the western languages Courland Livonian, Skolt Saami and Udmurt most known loanword strata are visible in UraLex. However, for the eastern Uralic languages Khanty and Nenets, very few loanwords are identified here, partially reflecting a western bias in materials available. Older Indo-European words shared across Uralic are visible in the sample as well as

subgroup-specific influence, e.g. Germanic in Finnic. The example languages also feature loanwords acquired independently, e.g. Latvian in Livonian, Russian in Skolt Saami and Tatar in Udmurt and family-internal borrowings, e.g. Komi in Khanty. More research is needed to further stratify and identify possible borrowings and discern inherited words from family-internal borrowings. The relatively low numbers of clear items indicate the need for evaluation of many etymologies.

In comparison to the six study languages, these other languages have substantial amounts of items of which the origin is not discussed in the literature, with the exception of Courland Livonian within the well-researched Finnic subgroup. The general proportions of loanwords in the western Uralic languages follow the expected sizes of the loanword layers for their subgroup which is confirmed by the studied languages. This may indicate moderate success in identifying loanwords in the basic vocabulary for these languages.

Section S2. Further prospects for refining borrowing profiles and applications for linguistic research

We used Uralic as a test case for examining the borrowing profile of a language as reflected by the loanword layers in basic vocabulary. It would be interesting to see whether our approach might be generally applicable for other language families as well.

Establishing borrowing profiles for Uralic languages with basic vocabulary is made possible by the diachronic research tradition in Uralic linguistics, where contact influence has primarily been studied through loanwords. In recent years, more attention has been given to family-internal borrowings and etymological nativization (e.g. Aikio, 2007; Metsäranta, 2018), and discussion of parallel borrowing has been incorporated in evaluative studies of loan etymologies (e.g. Holopainen, 2019). In the lexical domain, substrate studies are enjoying a renaissance, successfully contributing to Uralic etymology and reducing the number of words of unknown origin (e.g. Aikio, 2012; Saarikivi, 2006).

While the lexical material used to establish a borrowing profile still needs more research, the basic vocabulary approach could be applied in several fields of linguistic research:

- A) Language contact in lesser-documented languages. Assuming that basic research on sound history and etymology exists and the compilation of etymological information is possible, tracing borrowings in basic-vocabulary data would be a fruitful starting point for gaining an overview of language contacts even for less-documented languages, as basic-vocabulary lists are widely available.
- B) Phylogenetic historical linguistics. Some basic-vocabulary lists in conjunction with information on the cognacy of the items have been published as databases (Greenhill et al. 2008, Syrjänen et al. 2018, GLD) which have been employed in computational phylogenetic linguistics for studies on the genealogical relationships of languages. The borrowing profiles mediated through basic vocabulary could be utilized further to study the role of borrowing as one mechanism for change in a language's history. This could be worthwhile because, in addition to the identified loanwords, all datasets likely contain unidentified borrowings (McMahon & McMahon, 2005: 90). Loanwords have the potential to affect the tree-shapes and especially the timing of the language phylogenies, as they can e.g. contribute as innovations to the analysis. Further, it is usually not possible to differentiate between all borrowings and inherited words with narrow distributions in a large dataset, which could lead to the elimination of the wrong items (Chang et al. 2015: 205). Regarding timing analyses of language trees, carefully observing the behavior of borrowings is important because a

substantial amount of borrowing will cause the root of the tree to appear younger than it really is (Greenhill et al. 2009: 2303). Another possibility is that loanwords acting as synonyms for the basic meanings appear as singleton cognate sets and slow down the apparent rate of change, making the root inference older (for further discussion on rate of change see Verkerk, 2014). Finally, exclusion of borrowings can lead to empty basic vocabulary meaning slots misleadingly implying the total absence of the item in a language.

- C) Behavior of borrowings in basic vocabulary. Most loanwords in UraLex are the result of direct contacts between languages, with a few exceptions. With synonymy allowed, UraLex-type data would allow further tracking of the behavior of loanwords specifically in the basic vocabulary of a language. Already introduced in Haspelmath & Tadmor (2009: 49), explicitly coding whether borrowings co-exist with inherited words or if they have replaced an inherited word could offer additional material for e.g. evaluating the effects of widespread bilingualism.

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